

2030

NEUTRALPATH

Co-designed urban solutions for climate neutrality

About NEUTRALPATH

NEUTRALPATH paves the way towards climate-neutral cities through the development of positive and clean energy districts (PCEDs) and the co-design of efficient, climate-friendly solutions.

By contributing to **the European mission of achieving at least 100 climate-neutral and smart cities by 2030**, it sets an example for other cities to replicate the process by 2050.

What are PCEDs?

PCEDs are energy-efficient and energy-flexible urban areas of connected buildings. They are “clean energy” because they rely solely on renewable energy sources, and “positive” because they produce net zero greenhouse gas emissions and a surplus of renewable energy. PCEDs are crucial elements for enabling an effective and impactful urban transformation towards climate neutrality. The expertise acquired at the district level is essential for subsequent scale-up to the city level through the involvement of various socio-economic actors.

Lighthouse cities

Dresden and Zaragoza are the lighthouse cities of NEUTRALPATH. Together, they are pioneering to achieve climate neutrality and zero pollution by 2030, acting as experimentation and innovation hubs to help all European cities to follow suit by 2050. As lighthouse cities, Dresden and Zaragoza showcase the implementation of PCEDs throughout the entire process, from design to evaluation.

Dresden

Dresden focuses on the decarbonisation of district heating through geothermal energy and waste heat and the development of a low exergy system. Dresden PCED has virtual boundaries and connects 17 buildings in the Jessener Straße and the Van-Gogh- Straße districts.

Zaragoza

Zaragoza focuses on the reduction of thermal energy demand through façade renovation, window replacement and the use of innovative insulation materials as well as RES integration solutions in two residential and four public buildings in the Actur Rey Fernando district.

Actions

NEUTRALPATH carries out different specific innovation actions within the two PCEDs, both at the building and district levels. The actions can be grouped into different macro-categories.

Envelope retrofitting to reduce buildings' energy demand

High-efficient Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning, and Domestic Hot Water

Integrated Renewable Energy Sources (RES)

Grid management and energy control optimisation

E-mobility

Measures for communication and user acceptance

CN-Labs

NEUTRALPATH establishes five Climate-Neutral Labs (CN-Labs), one per each city involved. These labs act as centres for experimentation and innovation for strengthening the PCEDs' impact, in collaboration with the Cities Mission Platform. The CN-Labs have two main objectives: to actively involve local stakeholders and residents and to accelerate climate neutrality processes by sharing knowledge and facilitating insights exchange with other cities.

Fellow cities

Istanbul, Ghent and Vantaa are NEUTRALPATH's fellow cities. They collaborate with Zaragoza and Dresden to learn from their experiences and integrate the PCED concept into their decarbonisation strategy by 2050. Together, they are paving the way towards achieving common long-term goals.

Vantaa

Vantaa will design its PCED in the Aviapolis area to create the greenest airport city in Europe through ambitious plans for energy solutions, pedestrian routes, multimodal accessibility and green infrastructure.

Ghent

Ghent's strategy towards climate neutrality will involve the Muide Meulestede and Mariakerke districts and include the development of a neighbourhood heat network based on integrated RES.

Istanbul

Istanbul wants to transform the ex-industrial gasworks of Gazhane into an efficient climate-neutral lab. The PCED will include former gasworks turned into a recreational park, along with the addition of museums, workshops, and libraries.

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